

Blanchard River Project, Putnam County (41.02700, -84.05100)

Since construction in 2020, the Blanchard River Project, which was intended to allow the Blanchard River to overflow into a diversion channel, has rarely received water through its designed inflow because its elevation can only be reached under extremely high flow conditions. Instead, it is fed by backflow entering through the lower elevation designed outflow.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 27 acres of restored wetland, consisting of a floodplain channel and a series of isolated vernal pools between the floodplain channel and the river. During storm events the Blanchard River rises to flood its banks into the diversion channel before reconnecting with the Blanchard River downstream. During ambient conditions, the Blanchard River will backflow into the diversion channel from the lower portion of the channel. The isolated vernal pools only receive flood water during record flows and do not hold water for long. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm in which the Blanchard River floods its banks into the diversion channel.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar floodplain wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Improvements to the lower portion of the channel would facilitate retention and filtering of the backflow entering the outlet from the river year-round (i.e., consider implementing a means of controlling flow entering/exiting at River Lower).
- Planting vegetation along the banks of the lower channel would be more beneficial to nutrient uptake than the large rock that currently lines the banks, further promoting the floodplain function of that portion of the Project.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.